

1 **Aridity decouples C:N:P stoichiometry across multiple trophic levels in terrestrial**
2 **ecosystems**

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25 M.D-B. conceived the idea of this study. M.D-B. developed the conceptual basis for this
26 manuscript in consultation with P.B.R., D.J.E., F.T.M. and B.K.S. M.D-B. and D.J.E. conducted
27 field surveys. V.O., B.G., M.D-B. and F.T.M. carried out laboratory analyses. M.D-B. conducted
28 statistical modeling. The manuscript was written by M.D-B with contributions from all co-
29 authors.

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31

32 **Abstract**

33 Increases in aridity forecasted by the end of this century will decouple the cycles of soil carbon
34 (C), nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) in drylands –the largest terrestrial biome on Earth. Little is
35 known, however, about how changes in aridity simultaneously affect the C:N:P stoichiometry of
36 organisms across multiple trophic levels. It is imperative that we understand how aridity affects
37 ecological stoichiometry so that we can develop strategies to mitigate any effects of changing
38 climates. We characterized the C, N, P concentration and stoichiometry of soils, autotrophs
39 (trees, N-fixing shrubs, grasses and mosses) and heterotrophs (microbes and ants) across a wide
40 aridity gradient in Australia. Our results suggest that increases in aridity by the end of this
41 century may alter the C:N:P stoichiometry of heterotrophs (ants and microbes), non-woody plants
42 and in soil, but will not affect that one from woody-plants. In particular, increases in aridity were
43 positively related to C:P and N:P ratios in microbes and ants, negatively related to concentration
44 of C, and the C:N and C:P ratios in mosses and/or short grasses, and not related to the C:N:P
45 stoichiometry of either shrubs or trees. Because of the predominant role of C:N:P stoichiometry
46 in driving nutrient cycling, our findings provide useful contextual information to determine
47 ecological responses in a drier world.

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49 **Key words:** Carbon, Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Heterotrophs, Autotrophs, Soil Microbes, Ants

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63 **Introduction**

64 There is increasing evidence that projected increases of aridity by the end of this century (Feng
65 and Fu 2013; Huang and others 2016) will alter soil carbon (C), nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P)
66 cycles in terrestrial ecosystems (Delgado-Baquerizo and others 2013; Wang and others 2014;
67 Yuan and Chen 2015; Jiao and others 2016). In particular, aridity is expected to reduce the
68 concentrations of biologically controlled elements such as C and N in soils, as well as the soil
69 C:P and N:P ratios (Fig. 1). This expectation is based on the fact that aridity reduces the positive
70 effect of biotic components such as plants on C and N (e.g., via reductions in plant cover), but
71 increases concentrations of total P, which is primarily derived from rock weathering (Fig. 1;
72 Delgado-Baquerizo and others 2013). By impacting both biologically- and abiotically-controlled
73 elements in opposite ways, increasing aridity will potentially decouple (i.e., push in opposite
74 directions) the cycles of soil C and N vs. P. Though the impact of aridity on soil C:N:P
75 stoichiometry has been documented previously (Delgado-Baquerizo and others 2013; Wang and
76 others 2014; Yuan and Chen 2015; Jiao and others 2016), the simultaneous impacts of increased
77 aridity conditions on the nutrient concentrations and stoichiometric relationships in above- and
78 belowground biota are largely unknown.

79 Nutrient availability and stoichiometry play critical roles in regulating ecosystem
80 functions and services, such as nutrient cycling, habitat variability, litter decomposition and food
81 production and quality (Elser and others 2000; Sardans and others 2012; Zechmeister-Boltenstern
82 and others 2015). Thus, understanding the effects of increasing aridity on the nutrient economy
83 and stoichiometry of biotic components is necessary to adequately predict changes in ecosystem
84 functions and services in a more arid world. Assessing the impacts of aridity on stoichiometric
85 relationships is particularly important for drylands, as they cover 45% of Earth's land surface
86 (Právělie 2016) and their extent is predicted to increase by 11-23% by the end of this century
87 (Huang and others 2016). However, despite the importance of ecological stoichiometry for
88 ecosystem functioning (see Zechmeister-Boltenstern and others 2015 for a review), little is
89 known about whether the responses of C, N and P concentration and stoichiometry in
90 aboveground and belowground biota mirror those previously reported in dryland soils (Delgado-
91 Baquerizo and others 2013; He and others 2015; Jiao and others 2016). Furthermore, no previous
92 study has, to our knowledge, evaluated the simultaneous responses of multiple trophic levels to
93 predicted increases in aridity such as those forecasted with global change. Thus, the effects of

94 aridity on the C:N:P stoichiometry of multiple trophic levels, including plants, insects and
95 microbes are uncertain.

96 To advance our understanding of this important issue, we characterized the C, N, P
97 concentration and stoichiometry of soils, autotrophs (trees, N-fixing shrubs, grasses and biocrust-
98 forming mosses) and heterotrophs (microbes and ants) across a wide aridity gradient in eastern
99 Australia. We tested the hypothesis that the response of C:N:P stoichiometry of plants to
100 increases in aridity will be different from that of insects and microbes (Fig. 1). In particular, we
101 expect increases in C:P and N:P ratios in microbes and ants, and reductions in the concentration
102 of C, and the C:N and C:P ratios in mosses and/or short grasses with increases in aridity. The
103 main reasons supporting the divergent response of the C:N:P stoichiometry of plants and soil
104 organisms to increases in aridity include: 1) **differential capacity to obtain water**: perennial
105 plants in general, and woody plants in particular, are less reliant on surface water than insects
106 (e.g., ants) and near-surface microbes, as their root systems allow them to access water from
107 deeper soil layers, making them more resistant to increases in aridity; 2) **use of organic C**: unlike
108 heterotrophs, plants mainly obtain C from the atmosphere (but see Näsholm 1998) via
109 photosynthesis. Thus, reductions in photosynthetic rates linked to water stress may result in low
110 C concentration and C:N and C:P ratios; and 3) **Fast-growing rates**: insects and soil microbes
111 have rapid growth rates (compared with perennial plants) and are more mobile. Both require
112 considerable energy, hence they have a high P demand (Peñuelas and Sardans 2009).
113 Consequently, the tissues from heterotrophic organisms are often relatively richer in P, and have
114 lower C concentration and C:P and N:P ratios than those in perennial plants (Cease and others
115 2012; Cease and Elser 2013; Zechmeister-Boltenstern and others 2015; Carnicer and others
116 2015). More specifically, increasing water availability is known to enhance biological activity in
117 drylands (Whitford 1978; Frenette-Dussault and others 2013). Humid environments may promote
118 life strategies based on optimizing energy, which is required to support a growth energy-
119 demanding lifestyle. This requires comparatively high levels of N and P to sustain production
120 rates of P- and N-rich organelles and molecules such as ribosomes, ATP, DNA and RNA. Thus,
121 heterotrophic organisms may need to switch from a strategy of high energy investment (high P, N
122 and low C:P and N:P ratios; Fig. 1) to one that prioritizes investing in structure (low P, N and
123 high C:P and N:P ratios; Fig. 1; Reich and others 2014). This change in strategy respond to the
124 reduced capacity to obtain water and to tolerate increasing aridity under the most arid conditions

125 of heterotrophs compared to autotrophs. In fact, increases in aridity, which reduce microbial and
126 insect abundance and activity (Whitford 1978; Frenette-Dussault and others 2013; Delgado-
127 Baquerizo and others 2013; Maestre and others 2015), may favor a strategy based on optimizing
128 structure moving from a “resource acquisitive” versus “resource conservative” strategy (*sensu*
129 Chapin 1980 and Reich and others 2014). To survive in more arid environments, these organisms
130 will produce structures that promote desiccation tolerance, such as cell walls, structural proteins,
131 fatty acids, and waxy molecules; all of them mainly based on C or N chemistry leading to
132 increases in tissue C:P and N:P ratios (Csonka 1989; Schimel and others 2007). In addition, the
133 C:N:P stoichiometry of all autotrophic communities is not expected to respond in the same
134 manner to increases in aridity; with non-woody plants being more affected than woody plants as
135 a consequence of their lower capacity to obtain water and survive water stress. See Appendix S1
136 for additional rationale regarding the expected differing responses of woody vs. non-woody plant
137 species to increases in aridity (Fig. 1).

138

139 **Methods**

140 *Study area and sampling*

141 This study was carried out at 22 *Eucalyptus* forests from eastern Australia (Fig. S1). Locations
142 for this study were chosen to represent a wide range of aridity conditions (from arid to humid
143 ecosystems). Aridity Index (precipitation/potential evapotranspiration), total annual precipitation
144 and mean temperature ranged from 0.19 to 0.80, 280 mm to 1167 mm and from 12.8° C to 17.5°
145 C, respectively. Note that temperature was neither related to precipitation (Spearman’s $\rho = -$
146 0.121; $P = 0.592$; $n = 22$) nor to Aridity Index (Spearman’s $\rho = -0.123$; $P = 0.587$; $n = 22$) across
147 the sites studied. The underlying geology across these sites varied from Ordovician sedimentary
148 material in the east to Quaternary Pleistocene alluvium and colluvium on the western plains.
149 Despite the different geological substrates, the soils derived from these materials show marked
150 similarities, with generally gradational profiles and clay loam to loamy surface textures. We
151 surveyed areas of similar aspect, generally southerly, and slope (<2%) to minimize the influence
152 of factors other than climate in our conclusions. Perennial vegetation cover ranged from 18-98%.
153 Locations in this study were selected to always use the same genus/species of plants, mosses or
154 ants: *Eucalyptus* spp., *Acacia* spp., C3 native grass *Rhytidosperra* spp., biocrust-forming mosses

155 (*Barbula calycina*, *Campylopus* spp. and *Didymodon torquatus*), and soil-foraging ants
156 (*Iryidomyrmex purpureus*) (See Table S1 for a list of the species sampled at each plot).

157 Sampling was carried out in March 2014 (end of the dry-season). At each site, we
158 established a 30 m × 30 m plot. Aridity was determined as 1-Aridity Index [AI], where AI =
159 precipitation/potential evapotranspiration (UNEP 1992). We obtained values of the aridity index
160 (AI, precipitation/potential evapotranspiration) at 1 km resolution from Zomer and others (2008).
161 At each site, three soil cores (0-5 cm depth) were collected in open areas (bare ground without
162 mosses or any other visible biocrust component) between vegetation patches. Note that, in
163 drylands, nutrient availability and microbial activity mainly take place in the first few centimeters
164 of soils (Pointing and Belnap 2012). We focused on bare ground areas because microclimatic
165 amelioration by plant canopies may confound the effects of aridity on soil stoichiometry. Soil
166 cores were then mixed to obtain a composite soil sample for each microsite and site. A microsite
167 is defined as a microenvironment given by particular biotic (e.g., identify of plant species and
168 functional groups) and abiotic features (e.g. bare ground areas) within a particular location (i.e.,
169 at the local scale). After field sampling, the soil was sieved (2 mm mesh). Soil was air-dried
170 indoor (~35% humidity and ~25°C) for one month before physicochemical analyses. Previous
171 studies have found that air drying and further storage of dryland soils does not appreciably alter
172 variables such as those we studied (Zornoza and others 2006, 2009). Thus, the potential bias
173 induced by our drying treatment is expected to be minimal, as soils were already dry when we
174 collected them. Additionally, in most sites, we were able to collect leaf samples from grasses (n =
175 21), N-fixing shrubs (n = 21) and trees (n = 22), thalli from mosses (n = 20) and ants (n = 16).
176 See Table S1 for a list of the species sampled at each plot. In all cases, a composite sample from
177 ten individuals was collected per plot. Ants were directly collected from visible ant nests. Tissue
178 material was dried in the oven (70°C) and ground before chemical analyses. In the case of soil
179 mosses, we used an air compressor to remove any visible soil particle from the moss thalli to
180 reduce soil contamination as much as possible. Moreover, we would like to highlight that the
181 digestion procedures used here (explained below) to characterize P mainly focus on the organic
182 fractions –rather than on the mineral fractions, which are more abundant in soil–. In this respect,
183 any effect of soil contamination on the chemistry of soil mosses should have been fairly small.

184 *C:N:P measurements*

185 We measured the concentration of C, N and P in soils, non-woody short vascular (grasses) and

186 non-vascular plants (mosses), woody tall vascular plants (N-fixing shrubs and trees), soil
187 microbes and ants. For soils, we measured both total and available (i.e., soil solution pools) C, N,
188 and P concentrations and mass ratios. Soil available nutrients are readily available for plants and
189 microbes, but have high temporal (hours to days) and spatial variability. Total nutrients represent
190 a pool of nutrients that is much less variable, but is available for plants and microbes in the
191 longer term (years to centuries). The concentration of total organic C in soil, plants, mosses and
192 ants was determined as described in Anderson and Ingram (1993). Total N in these samples was
193 measured with a CN analyzer (LECO CHN628 Series, LECO Corporation, St Joseph, MI, USA);
194 total P was obtained using a SKALAR San++ Analyzer (Skalar, Breda, The Netherlands) after
195 digestion with sulphuric acid (three hours at 415°C) as described in Anderson and Ingram (1993).
196 The concentration of total available C (dissolved organic C) and N (sum of organic and inorganic
197 N) was measured from these extracts using a TOC/TON analyzer (TOC-Vsch, Shimadzu, Kyoto,
198 Japan) after 0.5 M K₂SO₄ extraction as described in Jones and Willet (2006). Olsen inorganic P
199 was measured following a 0.5M NaHCO₃ (pH: 8.5) extraction (Olsen and others 1954) and
200 determined colorimetrically (Tiessen and Moir 1993). Microbial biomass C, N and P was
201 determined using the fumigation-extraction method as explained in Voroney and others (2006).
202 Soil nutrient and microbial concentration were expressed on an oven-dry basis

203 *Statistical analyses*

204 We used a non-metric multidimensional ordination (NMDS) to explore overall variability in
205 multidimensional C, N and P concentration and ratios across the above- and belowground
206 components evaluated. These analyses allow us to visualize overall differences in the
207 concentrations and ratios of C, N and P across different belowground (soil total, available and
208 microbes) and aboveground (biocrust-mosses, grasses, N-fixing shrubs, trees and ants)
209 components at a glance. The two-dimensional NMDS solution provided a suitable representation
210 of the data (stress = 0.08; excellent to good stress according to Clarke 1993). Prior to these
211 analyses, data were standardized (z-transformed) and log₁₀-transformed to avoid
212 overrepresentation of particular variables in these analysis. We conducted NMDS analyses using
213 Euclidean distance with the PRIMER v6 statistical package for Windows (PRIMER-E Ltd.,
214 Plymouth Marine Laboratory, UK). We also calculated the correlations (Spearman's ρ) between
215 the axes of this NMDS with the concentrations and ratios of C, N and P to identify the variables
216 driving changes along these axes.

217 Most importantly, to test our hypotheses (Fig. 1) we calculated the correlations
218 (Spearman's ρ) between aridity (1-Aridity Index) and C, N and P concentration and ratios for the
219 different belowground and aboveground components evaluated. We used rank-based correlation
220 Spearman's ρ because this metric is robust to deviations from normality and is largely used in the
221 ecological literature (see Nakagawa and Cuthill 2007 for a review). To further test whether
222 Spearman's ρ differed significantly from zero, we assessed whether bias-corrected 95%-bootstrap
223 confidence intervals of Spearman's ρ did not overlap zero based on 9999 iterations (Rosenberg
224 and others 2000; see García-Palacios and others 2013 for a similar approach). Bias-corrected
225 95%-bootstrap confidence intervals is a much more conservative method than *P* values calculated
226 from Spearman rank correlations, explaining slightly differences between the significant levels
227 provided for these two methods.

228 Finally, we tested for overall differences between Aridity classes: Arid (Aridity Index <
229 0.50 –arid and semiarid) vs. Humid (Aridity Index > 0.50 –dry-subhumid and humid) ecosystems
230 for C, N and P concentration and ratios across belowground (soil total, soil available and soil
231 microbes) and aboveground components (biocrust-mosses, grasses, N-fixing shrubs, trees and,
232 ants and microbes) using a one-way ANOVA with Aridity class as a fixed factor.

233

234 **Results**

235 As expected, autotrophs (mosses, grasses, N-fixing shrubs and trees) had the highest mass C:P
236 ratios, while soils, ants and microbes had the lowest C:P ratio. Soil available and microbial C, N
237 and P comprised less than 5% of the total soil C, N and P concentrations. In general, trees and N-
238 fixing shrubs had the highest C concentration (Table 1). Ants, N-fixing shrubs and grasses had
239 the highest total concentrations of N and P, and soil available (i.e., nutrient pools) and microbes
240 had the lowest concentration of C, N and P along the aridity gradient studied (Table 1). N-fixing
241 shrubs and microbes/soil (total) showed the highest and lowest N:P ratios, respectively; and
242 trees/shrubs and microbes/ants had the highest and the lowest C:N ratios, respectively. Ordination
243 analyses separated organisms into two groups; 1) autotrophs (mosses, grasses, N-fixing shrubs
244 and trees) and 2) soil/soil organisms (Fig. 2; Table S2).

245 Aridity showed an overall negative correlation with total and available soil C, mosses and
246 grasses (Fig. 3), but did not correlated with C concentration in N-fixing shrubs, trees, microbes or
247 ants (Fig. 3). Aridity was negatively and positively correlated to N in soil available and ant

248 tissues, respectively, and positively and negatively correlated with the concentration of P in
249 microbes and soil (available), respectively. Similar results were found when we explored the
250 impacts of different aridity classes on C, N and P concentration and stoichiometry (Figs. S2 and
251 S3). Aridity was negatively correlated with the total soil C:P and N:P ratios, and positively
252 correlated with those of ants and microbes (Figs. 3 and S2), but was not correlated with those of
253 grasses, N-fixing shrubs and trees. C:P and C:N ratios of mosses were negatively correlated with
254 increasing aridity (Figs. 3 and S2).

255 At this point, we would like to clarify that, in the case of soil samples –we focused on
256 bare ground areas to avoid any confounding effects from plant litter on soil stoichiometry–,
257 however, soil chemistry is expected to be highly correlated in the selected microsites across our
258 aridity gradient. For example, preliminary analyses provided evidence that total soil C:N:P
259 concentrations and ratios were highly correlated across microsites (Table S3). Most importantly,
260 the correlations between aridity with total C:N:P concentrations and ratios are similar across
261 different microsites (Table S4). These analyses provide evidence that, in general, our results are
262 not bias by the choice of microsite.

263

264 **Discussion**

265 Our study provides evidence that increases in aridity differentially decouple C:N:P concentration
266 and stoichiometry in soil microbes, insects, grasses and mosses. In particular, our study suggests
267 a change in the life strategy of heterotrophs from one based on high growth and energy
268 investment (low C:P and N:P ratios) to one based on high structural investment (high C:P and
269 N:P ratios) along the aridity gradient studied. Moreover, we found reductions in leaf C (mosses
270 and grasses) and C:N and C:P ratios (grasses) for non-woody plants along this gradient, which
271 are consistent with previous results from a soil survey conducted in global drylands (Delgado-
272 Baquerizo and others 2013). Only woody plants (trees and shrubs) showed a high homeostasis to
273 aridity, as their C:N:P ratios and concentrations did not change along the aridity gradient studied.

274 As predicted (Fig. 1), microbial and ant C:P and N:P ratios increased along the aridity
275 gradient studied. In humid environments, maintaining a high microbial and ant activity will
276 require high levels of N and P to continue the production of P- and N-rich organelles and
277 molecules such as ribosomes, ATP, DNA and RNA (i.e., high energy strategy; Elser and others
278 2000; Sardans and others 2012; Zechmeister-Boltenstern and others 2015). In more arid

279 environments, however, strategies will depend on the ability to resist desiccation for extended
280 periods. Biological activity is known to be reduced with increasing aridity due to water stress in
281 drylands (Whitford 1978; Frenette-Dussault and others 2013; Delgado-Baquerizo and others
282 2013; Maestre and others 2015). To resist desiccation, it is known that insects can alter their
283 structure by reducing the permeability of the cuticle altering its lipid composition and/or
284 enhancing their tolerance to water loss by increasing hemolymph osmolality (Gibbs and others
285 1997; Weldon and others 2016). Similarly, soil microbes can survive desiccation as dormant
286 inocula by accumulating C- and N-demanding solutes in their cells to reduce water potential and
287 to maintain hydration (Csonka 1989; Schimel and others 2007). Other structures used by soil
288 microbes and insects to resist desiccation include cell walls, and structural proteins, fatty acids,
289 and waxy molecules, all of them requiring high amounts of C (Gibbs and others 1997; Weldon
290 and others 2016).

291 Several mechanisms might help to explain the differential responses of C:N:P
292 concentration and stoichiometry of non-woody (grasses and mosses) vs. woody (trees and shrubs)
293 plants. In particular, we predicted that larger vascular plants such as trees and N-fixing shrubs are
294 more independent of topsoil water than shorter vascular and non-vascular plants because their
295 well-developed root systems allow them to access moisture stored at deeper layers in the soil
296 (Walter 1939; Ward and others 2013) (Appendix S1). Conversely, shorter vascular and non-
297 vascular plants have smaller (or rudimentary) root systems, which make them more vulnerable to
298 increases in aridity. Dryland mosses, however, lack of a complex root system and are not reliant
299 on soil moisture for hydration, as they have mechanisms to trap water from atmospheric sources
300 (e.g., dew and fog; Pan and others 2016). The two-layer hypothesis of Walters (1939) predicts a
301 strong vertical niche partitioning of water, with grasses accessing surface horizons (generally <
302 50 cm deep) while woody plants have a greater access to deeper, sub-soil moisture. A recent
303 meta-analysis demonstrated strong support for this phenomenon in environments ranging from
304 deserts to mesic savannas (Ward and others 2013). Thus, woody plants (trees and shrubs) have a
305 greater capacity to obtain water than non-woody plants (mosses and grasses), but also a higher
306 transpiration rate and ability to regulate water loss (Mazzacuallo and Kulmatiski 2015). This
307 greater capacity may help woody plants to maintain photosynthetic rates, hence C-fixation. In
308 contrast, shorter vascular and non-vascular plants such as short grasses and mosses will be active
309 for a shorter period in response to low water availability, fixing less atmospheric C (Walters

310 1939; Ward and others 2013). This would explain the lower C (mosses and grasses) and C:P and
311 C:N ratios (mosses) observed with increasing aridity. These results are consistent with those from
312 a previous study showing a positive correlation between total annual rainfall and the leaf C:N and
313 C:P ratios in a grass species from Chinese arid regions (He and others 2015). We would like to
314 highlight that the relatively lower leaf C concentration in grasses compared to trees and shrubs
315 might be a consequence of the high silicon content often found in grass foliage and which
316 provides some of the structure that dicotyledons obtain from C-rich compounds (Shewmaker et
317 al. 1987). This should not bias, however, the conclusions from our study as, if this occurred, this
318 artefact should not alter the C:N:P ratios in grass leaves.

319 Our results have implications for predicting the potential consequences of increasing
320 aridity on ecosystem functions and services (e.g., carbon storage and nutrient cycling), and on
321 long-term life evolution in drylands. For example, our study provides evidence that C (grasses
322 and mosses) and C:N and C:P ratios (mosses) in non-woody plants will decline with increasing
323 aridity (i.e., without accounting for dispersal limitations). Some of these changes in C, C:N and
324 C:P stoichiometry in mosses and grasses may be indirectly driven by changes in species
325 composition from mesic to more arid ecosystems (Table S1). Moreover, the cover of grasses (but
326 not mosses; Delgado-Baquerizo and others 2016a) declines with increasing aridity ($\rho_{\text{grasses}} = -$
327 0.41 , $P = 0.064$) along the same gradient (Delgado-Baquerizo and others 2016a). A lower C
328 fixation by grasses and mosses, with an averaged total ground cover in the studied sites of 25%
329 and 10%, respectively (Delgado-Baquerizo and others 2016a), will likely reduce the capacity of
330 drylands to fix atmospheric C. Although the effect of aridity on small autotrophs is obvious from
331 our data, it is important to highlight the fact that elevated $[\text{CO}_2]$ may enhance water use
332 efficiency (WUE) in C3 plants and therefore C fixation in drylands (Evans and others 2014),
333 which may potentially mitigate some of the reported negative effects of aridity on leaf C and C:N
334 and C:P ratios. Whether an increase in WUE due to rising CO_2 can compensate for the negative
335 effects of increased aridity on water availability and C fixation is largely unknown. However, it
336 has been recently observed that increased $[\text{CO}_2]$ cannot fully compensate for the negative impacts
337 of aridity on plant growth (Brookshire and Weaver 2015).

338 Additionally, shifts in tissue stoichiometry of soil microbes and mosses in response to
339 increasing aridity will likely influence the rates at which essential processes such as soil organic
340 matter decomposition and mineralization occur in drylands, which are largely controlled by litter

341 quality and microbial stoichiometry. For example, a reduction in leaf tissue C:N ratio with
342 increasing aridity may promote higher mineralization rates beneath mosses, leading to nutrient
343 losses to the subsoil and atmosphere (Dijkstra et al. 2012). More than impacting ecosystem
344 functioning in the medium term (years to centuries), increases in aridity could promote
345 evolutionary long-term changes in the stoichiometry of soil microbes, insects and short plants. A
346 recent study highlighted the importance of human legacies for plant stoichiometry during
347 domestication and their implications for ecosystem functioning (i.e., nutrient cycling; Delgado-
348 Baquerizo and others 2016b). Similarly, changes in life stoichiometry with increasing aridity may
349 condition long-term evolutionary trends in drylands by selecting plants, microbes and insects
350 with different levels of C, N and P in their structures, potentially altering ecosystem structure and
351 functioning (Peñuelas and others 2012).

352 **Conclusions**

353 To our knowledge, our results provide, for the first time, an assessment of the effects of aridity on
354 the stoichiometry of multiple aboveground (ants, woody and non-woody plants) and
355 belowground (soil microbes) communities. Our results suggest that increases in aridity by the end
356 of this century will likely alter the C:N:P stoichiometry of heterotrophs (ants and microbes), non-
357 woody plants and in soil, but will not affect that one from woody-plants. In particular, our results
358 indicate that increases in aridity will likely increase the C:P and N:P ratios of microbes and ants,
359 and will decrease the concentration of C, and the C:N and C:P ratios in mosses and/or short
360 grasses. Our findings strongly suggest that the response of C:N:P stoichiometry of multiple
361 trophic levels needs to be considered simultaneously if we want to properly assess ecological
362 responses to a more arid world.

363 **Acknowledgements**

364 This study was supported by the Australian Research Council (project DP13010484;
365 DP170104634), by GRDC (UWS00008) and by the European Research Council (ERC) under the
366 European Community's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013)/ERC Grant agreement
367 n° 242658 (BIOCOM). M.D-B. also acknowledge support from the Marie Skłodowska-Curie
368 Actions of the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme H2020-MSCA-IF-2016 under REA grant
369 agreement n° 702057. DJE was supported by the Hermon Slade Foundation. FTM acknowledges
370 support from the European Research Council (BIODESERT project, ERC Grant agreement n°
371 647038) and by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (BIOMOD project,

372 CGL2013-44661-R).

373 **Data accessibility**

374 Data associated with this paper has been deposited in figshare:
375 <https://figshare.com/s/d736cb67a3397d3c7f1c> (10.6084/m9.figshare.5056486).

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527 **Table 1.** Mean values (\pm SE) of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus concentration and ratios in soil
528 total and available (n = 22), microbes (n = 19), grasses (leaf; n = 21), N-fixing shrubs (leaf; n =
529 21), trees (leaf; n = 22), mosses (thalli; n = 20) and ants (body; n = 16) along the studied aridity
530 gradient. Soil nutrient and microbial concentration were expressed on an oven-dry basis.

	Soil		Autotrophs				Heterotrophs	
	Soil total	Soil available	Biocrust-mosses	Grasses	N-fixing shrubs	Trees	Ants	Microbes
C (%)	2.22 (0.32)	$1.59 \cdot 10^{-2}$ ($1.52 \cdot 10^{-3}$)	17.04 (1.76)	44.05 (1.16)	55.52 (1.01)	53.88 (0.78)	47.76 (4.54)	$1.59 \cdot 10^{-2}$ ($3.70 \cdot 10^{-3}$)
N (%)	0.14 (0.02)	$2.21 \cdot 10^{-3}$ ($2.50 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	0.59 (0.08)	1.43 (0.14)	2.07 (0.13)	1.22 (0.09)	7.56 (0.87)	$3.08 \cdot 10^{-3}$ ($6.70 \cdot 10^{-4}$)
P (%)	0.02 (0.00)	$2.10 \cdot 10^{-4}$ ($4.00 \cdot 10^{-5}$)	0.05 (0.01)	0.08 (0.01)	0.08 (0.01)	0.07 (0.01)	0.43 (0.06)	$6.30 \cdot 10^{-4}$ ($1.60 \cdot 10^{-4}$)
C:P	119.70 (18.65)	184.84 (53.46)	440.71 (74.61)	722.15 (110.31)	860.17 (99.89)	872.67 (72.39)	125.35 (13.65)	34.28 (6.38)
N:P	6.88 (0.66)	24.70 (7.10)	12.53 (1.34)	18.64 (1.07)	28.10 (1.84)	17.92 (0.98)	19.04 (2.23)	7.03 (1.07)
C:N	16.61 (1.44)	7.41 (0.35)	36.32 (6.44)	37.54 (4.05)	29.99 (2.92)	48.86 (3.68)	6.86 (0.45)	5.80 (1.01)

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Figure 1. Conceptual framework exploring how ecological stoichiometry responds to increases in aridity for soil, autotrophic and heterotrophic organisms.

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558 **Figure 2.** Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) (stress = 0.08) plots showing the relative
 559 differences in C:N:P chemistry and stoichiometry for soil, autotrophic and heterotrophic
 560 organisms. Data are mean values \pm SE for 22 plots. Boxes to the right and below the figure
 561 include significant correlations (Spearman's ρ) between C:N:P concentration and ratios with the
 562 NMDS axes.

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569 **Aridity effect (Spearman rho)**

570 **Figure 3.** Aridity effects (Spearman's ρ) on C:N:P chemistry and ratios of soil, autotrophic and

571 heterotrophic organisms. The bars around the means are bias-corrected 95% bootstrap confidence

572 intervals. Negative/positive mean Spearman's ρ indicate negative/positive impacts of aridity on a

573 particular C:N:P element and ratio. Significance levels are as follows: ^a $P < 0.10$, $*P < 0.05$, $**P$

574 < 0.01

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577 **Supplementary information**

578 **Table S1.** Aridity Index and aridity and species of vascular plant (*Acacia*, *Eucalyptus*,
579 *Rhytidosperma*), mosses and ant in each location.

580 **Table S2.** Correlation (Spearman) among soil, autotrophic and heterotrophic organisms for soil
581 carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus concentration and ratios. Significance levels are as follows: ^aP <
582 0.10, *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001.

583 **Table S3.** Correlation (Spearman) between soil carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus concentration
584 and ratios in bare soil and that one in other microsites.

585 **Table S4.** Correlation (Spearman) between aridity and soil carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus
586 concentration and ratios across different microsites.

587 **Figure S1.** Locations of the study sites. Color patterns indicate aridity (1 – aridity index)
588 gradients. Aridity increases from green to purple in the graphs.

589 **Figure S2.** Mean values (\pm SE) of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus ratios in soils (available and
590 total), plants, ants and microbes for arid and semiarid (Aridity Index < 0.50) vs. dry-subhumid
591 and humid (Aridity Index > 0.50) regions. Differences between aridity classes (arid vs. humid;
592 fixed factor) from a one-way ANOVA are as follows: *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001.

593 **Figure S3.** Mean values (\pm SE) of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations in soils
594 (available and total), plants, ants and microbes for arid and semiarid (Aridity Index < 0.50) vs.
595 dry-subhumid and humid (Aridity Index > 0.50) regions. Differences between aridity classes
596 (arid vs. humid; fixed factor) from a one-way ANOVA are as follows: ^aP < 0.10, *P < 0.05, **P
597 < 0.01, ***P < 0.001.

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608 **Supplementary information**

609 **Appendix S1. Differential response of plant stoichiometry to increasing aridity.**

610 Given the variable capacity of different plant types (i.e., non-vascular plants vs. vascular plants
611 and woody vs. non-woody plants) to obtain water, we posit that reductions in water availability
612 under increased aridity conditions will differentially alter the nutrient stoichiometry of non-
613 vascular (mosses), short non-woody (grasses) and tall woody (shrubs and trees) plants. In
614 particular, we hypothesize that the C:N:P stoichiometry of large vascular woody plants such as
615 trees and shrubs may be highly resistant (i.e., remain unchanged) to increases in aridity (Fig. 1).
616 The notion that woody plants and grasses access different regions of the soil profile has been
617 widely accepted since Walter's (1939) two-layer hypothesis. This hypothesis predicts a strong
618 vertical niche partitioning of water, with short non-woody plants (e.g., grasses) accessing surface
619 horizons while tall woody plants have a greater access to deeper, sub-soil moisture (Ward and
620 others 2013). Dryland mosses, however, are not reliant on soil moisture for hydration, and instead
621 trap water coming from dew and fog events with fine hair points on the ends of the leaves (Pan
622 and others 2016). Thus, in comparison to non-vascular (mosses) and short, non-woody plants
623 (grasses), tall woody plants invest in deep root systems that allow them to obtain water from the
624 deeper soil layers and maintain higher levels of water regulation in response to increases in
625 aridity. This capability will allow certain levels of C and N (via associated cyanobacteria)
626 fixation from the atmosphere and nutrient acquisition (e.g., via release of enzymes and carboxylic
627 acids; Bowker and others 2008; Bell and others 2013) in the most arid environments. Conversely,
628 mosses and short non-woody plants have no root system or a more rudimentary system than tall
629 woody plants. This may limit their capacity to obtain water and to fix C from the atmosphere
630 under the most arid conditions, resulting in decreases in C concentrations and in the C:P and C:N
631 ratios.

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639 **Table S1.** Aridity Index and aridity and species of vascular plant (*Acacia*, *Eucalyptus*,
640 *Rhytidosperma*), mosses and ant in each location.
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Site name	Aridity Index	Biome	N-fixing shrubs	Trees	Grasses	Mosses	Ants
BU1	0.199	Arid	<i>Acacia oswaldii</i>	<i>Eucalyptus largiflorens</i>	<i>Rytidosperma caespitosum</i>	<i>Didymodon torquatus</i>	
BU2	0.203	Arid	<i>Acacia oswaldii</i>	<i>Eucalyptus largiflorens</i>	<i>Rytidosperma caespitosum</i>	<i>Didymodon torquatus</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
CYP028	0.364	Arid	<i>Acacia decora</i>	<i>Eucalyptus populnea</i>	<i>Rytidosperma caespitosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	
JM055	0.308	Arid	<i>Acacia decora</i>	<i>Eucalyptus populnea</i>	<i>Rytidosperma caespitosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM057	0.317	Arid		<i>Eucalyptus populnea</i>		<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM060	0.332	Arid	<i>Acacia decora</i>	<i>Eucalyptus populnea</i>	<i>Rytidosperma racemosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM061	0.353	Arid	<i>Acacia decora</i>	<i>Eucalyptus populnea</i>	<i>Rytidosperma racemosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM062	0.423	Arid	<i>Acacia decora</i>	<i>Eucalyptus microcarpa</i>	<i>Rytidosperma racemosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM065	0.610	Humid	<i>Acacia genistifolia</i>	<i>Eucalyptus rossii</i>	<i>Rytidosperma racemosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM071	0.654	Humid	<i>Acacia implexa</i>	<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i>	<i>Rytidosperma pilosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM072	0.652	Humid	<i>Acacia implexa</i>	<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i>	<i>Rytidosperma pilosum</i>		<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM076	0.580	Humid	<i>Acacia implexa</i>	<i>Eucalyptus rossii</i>	<i>Rytidosperma racemosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM077	0.473	Humid	<i>Acacia dealbata</i>	<i>Eucalyptus microcarpa</i>	<i>Rytidosperma racemosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM079	0.444	Humid	<i>Acacia dealbata</i>	<i>Eucalyptus microcarpa</i>	<i>Rytidosperma racemosum</i>		<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM081	0.432	Arid	<i>Acacia decora</i>	<i>Eucalyptus populnea</i>	<i>Rytidosperma caespitosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM085	0.465	Arid	<i>Acacia decora</i>	<i>Eucalyptus populnea</i>	<i>Rytidosperma caespitosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	
JM092	0.429	Arid	<i>Acacia decora</i>	<i>Eucalyptus populnea</i>	<i>Rytidosperma caespitosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
JM100	0.762	Humid	<i>Acacia decora</i>	<i>Eucalyptus rossii</i>	<i>Rytidosperma racemosum</i>	<i>Campylopus introflexus</i>	
Site 1	0.286	Arid	<i>Acacia wilhelmiana</i>	<i>Eucalyptus socialis</i>	<i>Rytidosperma caespitosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	
Site 2	0.296	Arid	<i>Acacia wilhelmiana</i>	<i>Eucalyptus socialis</i>	<i>Rytidosperma caespitosum</i>	<i>Barbula calycina</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
Site 3	0.798	Humid	<i>Acacia implexa</i>	<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i>	<i>Rytidosperma pilosum</i>	<i>Campylopus introflexus</i>	<i>Iridomyrmex purpureus</i>
Site 4	0.920	Humid	<i>Acacia implexa</i>	<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i>	<i>Rytidosperma pilosum</i>	<i>Campylopus introflexus</i>	

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650 **Table S2.** Correlation (Spearman) among soil, autotrophic and heterotrophic organisms for soil
 651 carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus concentration and ratios. Significance levels are as follows: ^a*P* <
 652 0.10, **P* < 0.05, ***P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.001.

Element	Variable	Total	Available	Microbes	Tree	N-fixing shrubs	Grasses	Biocrusts- mosses
Carbon	Available	0.736**						
	Microbes	0.537**	0.482*					
	Tree	-0.073	-0.427*	-0.215				
	N-fixing shrubs	-0.061	-0.018	-0.061	0.266			
	Grasses	0.169	0.058	-0.192	0.188	0.255		
	Biocrusts	0.140	0.370	0.027	-0.114	-0.139	-0.077	
	Ants	0.076	0.088	0.224	0.018	0.246	-0.211	-0.042
Nitrogen	Available	0.754**						
	Microbes	0.669**	0.492*					
	Tree	0.155	0.217	0.004				
	N-fixing shrubs	0.364	0.258	0.255	0.444*			
	Grasses	0.052	0.318	0.158	0.192	0.042		
	Biocrusts	0.226	0.056	0.080	0.468*	0.779**	-0.204	
	Ants	0.257	0.075	-0.093	0.236	-0.207	0.311	0.132
Phosphorus	Available	0.468*						
	Microbes	-0.044	-0.379					
	Tree	0.163	0.100	-0.470*				
	N-fixing shrubs	0.171	-0.040	-0.071	0.627**			
	Grasses	-0.039	-0.010	-0.073	0.186	0.217		
	Biocrusts	0.328	0.199	-0.301	0.532*	0.614**	-0.202	
	Ants	0.268	-0.023	-0.037	0.261	0.029	-0.057	0.385
C:P	Available	0.771**						
	Microbes	-0.289	-0.401					
	Tree	0.092	0.005	0.000				
	N-fixing shrubs	0.090	0.147	-0.075	0.536*			
	Grasses	0.112	0.126	-0.247	0.275	0.338		
	Biocrusts	0.432	0.577*	-0.321	0.271	0.132	0.039	
	Ants	-0.600*	-0.555*	0.398	0.425	0.411	0.082	-0.044
N:P	Available	0.910**						
	Microbes	-0.500*	-0.331					
	Tree	0.063	0.275	-0.123				

	N-fixing shrubs	0.013	0.119	-0.143	0.429			
	Grasses	0.045	0.212	0.024	0.406	0.558**		
	Biocrusts	0.125	0.162	0.000	0.072	-0.246	0.328	
	Ants	-0.600*	-0.538	0.116	0.357	0.475	0.418	-0.176
C:N	Available	-0.020						
	Microbes	0.328	-0.110					
	Tree	0.301	0.263	0.248				
	N-fixing shrubs	0.348	0.026	0.079	0.426			
	Grasses	-0.012	0.123	-0.284	0.230	0.152		
	Biocrusts	0.137	0.242	0.230	0.295	0.167	0.123	
	Ants	0.046	0.175	0.050	0.039	-0.075	0.364	0.357

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675 **Table S3.** Correlation (Spearman) between soil carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus concentration
 676 and ratios in bare soil and that one in other microsites.

Microsite	Parameter	C	N	P	CP	NP	CN
N-fixing shrub	ρ	0.352	0.635	0.754	0.605	0.842	-0.034
	P-value	0.108	0.001	< 0.001	0.003	< 0.001	0.879
Biocrusts	ρ	0.500	0.738	0.887	0.840	0.784	0.737
	P-value	0.018	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Trees	ρ	0.755	0.491	0.661	0.730	0.582	0.389
	P-value	< 0.001	0.020	0.001	< 0.001	0.004	0.074
Grasses	ρ	0.658	0.719	0.852	0.656	0.774	0.465
	P-value	0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.001	< 0.001	0.034
Ant nests	ρ	0.642	0.579	0.604	0.811	0.810	0.476
	P-value	0.001	0.005	0.003	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.025

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695 **Table S4.** Correlation (Spearman) between aridity and soil carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus
 696 concentration and ratios across different microsites.

Microsite	Parameter	C	N	P	CP	NP	CN
N-fixing shrub	ρ	-0.496	-0.366	0.152	-0.654	-0.762	-0.029
	P-value	0.019	0.093	0.500	0.001	< 0.001	0.899
Bare soil	ρ	-0.610	-0.273	0.260	-0.771	-0.862	-0.205
	P-value	0.003	0.219	0.242	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.360
Biocrusts	ρ	-0.337	0.001	0.256	-0.740	-0.601	-0.418
	P-value	0.125	0.998	0.251	< 0.001	0.003	0.053
Trees	ρ	-0.510	-0.327	0.181	-0.657	-0.602	-0.167
	P-value	0.015	0.138	0.420	0.001	0.003	0.459
Grasses	ρ	-0.317	-0.105	0.147	-0.527	-0.658	-0.108
	P-value	0.162	0.650	0.526	0.014	0.001	0.642
Ant nests	ρ	-0.371	-0.020	0.366	-0.678	-0.697	-0.412
	P-value	0.089	0.930	0.093	0.001	< 0.001	0.057

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708 **Figure S1.** Locations of the study sites. Color patterns indicate aridity (1 – aridity index)
709 gradients. Aridity increases from green to purple in the graphs.

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727 **Figure S2.** Mean values (\pm SE) of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus ratios in soil (available and
 728 total), plants, ants and microbes for arid and semi-arid (Aridity Index < 0.50) vs. dry-subhumid
 729 and humid (Aridity Index > 0.50) regions. Differences between aridity classes (arid vs. humid;
 730 fixed factor) from a one-way ANOVA are as follows: ^a $P < 0.10$, $*P < 0.05$, $**P < 0.01$, $***P <$
 731 0.001 .

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733 **Figure S3.** Mean values (\pm SE) of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations in soil
734 (available and total), plants, ants and microbes for arid and semiarid (Aridity Index < 0.50) vs.
735 dry-subhumid and humid (Aridity Index > 0.50) regions. Differences between aridity classes
736 (arid vs. humid; fixed factor) from a one-way ANOVA are as follows: ^a $P < 0.10$, * $P < 0.05$, ** P
737 < 0.01 , *** $P < 0.001$.

738 **References (not listed in the main text)**

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